

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

CoFe₂O₄ as a source of Co(II) ions for *in situ* oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide using peroxymonosulfate: influence of process parameters and solid surface changes

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Abbreviations

AsP – As-prepared samples without *in situ* chemical activation using oxidizer

Cpt 400 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h

Cpt 700 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h

CMF: cobalt magnetic ferrite

DMPO - 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline *N*-oxide

ESR - electron spin resonance

EI - electrochemical impedance

HRTEM – high-resolution transmission electron microscopy

HO• – hydroxyl radical

HPLC – high-performance liquid chromatography

ICP-OES – inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry

IMD – Imidacloprid insecticide

IMD fraction – $100 \times [\text{IMD}]_t / [\text{IMD}]_0$: [IMD] concentration at a specific time (*t*) and *t* = 0

ISCO – *in situ* chemical activation

MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry

¹O₂ – singlet oxygen

PDS – peroxydisulfate

PMS – peroxymonosulfate

SO₄•⁻ – sulfate radical

SG 400 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h

SG700 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h

UHPLC-QToF MS – ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass analyzer

Us – Assayed samples for the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS to oxidize IMD

XRD – X-ray diffraction

XPS – X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Table S1 Some reference papers that utilize CoFe_2O_4 and PMS, as oxidizer, to examine the concentration and role of Co(II) ions that have leached into the assayed solution.

Reference	Compound	Experimental conditions highlights	Co(II) ion leaching issue
[1]	Magnetic CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles supported on titanate nanotubes - $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{TNTs}$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrothermal synthesis of TNTs - $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{TNTs}$ composite synthesized by impregnation + calcination - Rhodamine B and phenol; catalyst dosage: 10 mg to 21 mg; Oxone = 4 g L⁻¹ 	The composite led to significant reduction of Co(II) ion leaching (from 928 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 662 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).
[2]	CoFe_2O_4 @Graphene hybrid aerogels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hybrid aerogels synthesized by freeze-drying - Flowing experiments: 25 to 100 mg L⁻¹ organic (indigo carmine, methyl orange, orange II, malachite green, phenol and norfloxacin), PMS solution (0.2–0.6 g L⁻¹), flow rates of 60, 90, or 120 mL h⁻¹ 	All experimental conditions led to Co(II) ion leaching lower than 1 mg L ⁻¹ .
[3]	$\text{Co}_3\text{Fe}_7\text{-CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ composite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Salt precursor + 2-methylimidazole followed by pyrolysis under N₂ atmosphere - 2,4-Dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP: 50 mg L⁻¹, 200 mL) + catalyst (0.05 g L⁻¹) + PMS (1.25 g L⁻¹) - Optimum pH: 7.7 	The detected concentration of Co and Fe ions were 0.052 and 0.036 mg L ⁻¹ , respectively. Low 2,4-DCP oxidation (20% in 30 min) was reported for the homogeneous reaction.
[4]	Expanded graphite (EG) loaded with CoFe_2O_4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-precipitation using salt precursors + EG (700 °C/1 min) thermally treated at 400 °C/2 h Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) at 10 mg/L: investigation of EG/CoFe_2O_4 mass ratio, catalyst dose (0 – 0.8 g L⁻¹), PMS concentration (0 – 0.4 mM), initial pH (3 – 11), SMX initial concentration (2.5 – 15 mg L⁻¹), and interfering ions (Cl^-, HCO_3^-, and HPO_4^{2-}) 	Co and Fe leaching equal to 0.129 mg L ⁻¹ and 0.025 mg/L, respectively, without investigation of homogeneous reactions.

Table S1 (continuation) Some reference papers that utilize CoFe_2O_4 and PMS, as oxidizer, to examine the concentration and role of Co(II) ions that have leached into the assayed solution.

[5]	$\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ with different molar ratios of Co:Fe (1:16, 1:8, 1:4, 1:2, and 3:4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-precipitation using salt precursors + heat treatment at 600 °C/1 h - SMX (10 mg L⁻¹): investigation of catalyst dose (0.05, 0.1, and 0.2 g L⁻¹), PMS concentration (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 g L⁻¹), solution pH (3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0, and 11.0), interfering ions (Cl^-, HCO_3^-, NO_3^-, and SO_4^{2-}) 	The Fe and Co concentration was 0.32 and 0.43 mg L ⁻¹ , respectively, after the 5 th cycle. Only a small contribution from homogeneous reactions (17% - solution pH unknown) was observed. Co ion concentration also ranged from 0.2 to 0.7 mg L ⁻¹ depending on the solution pH.
[6]	CoFe_2P_x synthesized by phosphorization of CoFe_2O_4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrothermal synthesis of CoFe_2O_4 followed by its low temperature phosphorization using NaH_2PO_2 - Sulphachloropyridazine sodium (SCP) as target pollutant: investigation of distinctly prepared compounds and oxidants, pH values, PMS concentration, and catalyst dosage 	The reported leached Co ions during the recycling test (5 cycles) were very low and equal to 0.082, 0.053, 0.027, 0.024, and 0.023 mg L ⁻¹ . No homogeneous experiments were carried out.
[7]	Core-shell $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3@\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ hybrids microspheres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ion exchange calcination method - Phenol (10 mg L⁻¹) as target pollutant: investigation of catalyst dosage (5, 10, 20, 30 mg L⁻¹), PMS concentration (1, 2, 3, 4 mM), initial pH (3, 5, 7, 9), solution temperature (25, 35, 45, 55 °C), interfering ion (SO_4^{2-}, Cl^-). 	The reported Co ion leached after the first cycle (during the recycling test) was 0.0198 mg L ⁻¹ . Further measurements were below the detection limit. No homogeneous experiment was carried out

Table S1 (continuation) Some reference papers that utilize CoFe₂O₄ and PMS, as oxidizer, to examine the concentration and role of Co(II) ions that have leached into the assayed solution..

[8]	CoFe bimetallic composite (CoFe@FS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solvothermal synthesis of CoFe@FS - Ciprofloxacin (100 mL at 10 mg L⁻¹): investigation of catalyst load (0.05, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 g L⁻¹), PMS concentration (1, 1.5, 2, 2.5 mM), initial CIP concentration (5, 10, 20, 50 mg L⁻¹), initial pH (2.99, 5.09, 7.02, 9.01), temperature (5, 15, 25, 35 °C), inorganic (Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻ and HCO₃⁻) and organic (humic acid) interferents 	Up to 0.7 mg L ⁻¹ of Co ions was detected. Homogeneous experiments were carried out, but led to a lower oxidation rate and level with respect to the CoFe@FS.
[9]	CoFe ₂ O ₄ supported on three-dimensional graphene aerogels (CoFe ₂ O ₄ @3DG)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrothermal synthesis of CoFe₂O₄ from salt precursors and graphene oxide. - Benzotriazole (BTA: 100 mg L⁻¹ for 100 mL): investigation of the CoFe₂O₄ composite (CoFe₂O₄@3DG, CoFe₂O₄@rGO, CoFe₂O₄, 3DG), pH (3, 5, 7, 9, 11), PMS concentration (4–16 mmol L⁻¹) 	The amount of Co ion leached ranged from 0.18 mg L ⁻¹ to 0.35 mg L ⁻¹ after the 7th cycle during the stability test of CoFe ₂ O ₄ @3DG.
[10]	CoFe ₂ O ₄ nanoparticles dispersed in a oil sludge carbon (OSC), previously activated - CoFe ₂ O ₄ /OSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil sludge activation mixed with Co and Fe salt precursor and followed by heat treatment. - Norfloxacin (30 μM) as target pollutant: investigation of initial pH (3.2, 4.5, 5.9, 7, 8.4), PMS concentration (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1 mM), catalyst dosage (0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 1 g L⁻¹), temperature, and cycles of catalyst (10 experiments). 	The amount of Co ion leaching increased with the recycling experiments (from ~10 μg L ⁻¹ to 50 μg L ⁻¹). Acidic solutions also led to higher Co ion amounts. No homogeneous experiment was carried out.

Table S2 Instrumental parameters optimized during ICP-OES analyses.

Parameters	Values
Integration time for the emission line (s)	5
Sample flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	4.2
Sample flow rate during analysis (mL min ⁻¹)	2.1
Peristaltic pump stabilization time (s)	25
Applied radio frequency power (W)	1200
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.25
Nebulizing gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.83
Cooling gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	16
Co emission line used (nm) and signal observation	228.616 (Axial)
Fe emission line used (nm) and signal observation	259.940 (Axial)

Fig. S1 Chemical structure of imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide - C₉H₁₀ClN₅O₂ and MW: 255.6615486 g mol⁻¹.

Ion composition of tap water and some of its physicochemical parameters can be seen below.

Table S3 Chemical composition of tap H₂O

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	6.14 – 6.20 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	32 μS cm ⁻¹ (21.2 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)*	0.0
[Na ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.85
[K ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.96
[Mg ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.47
[Ca ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.61
[Br ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	5.32
[Cl ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.58
[F ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	Traces (not quantified)
[SO ₄ ²⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.28

*Total organic carbon (TOC) measurement carried out as described in [11].

Text S1

Simulated municipal wastewater (SMWW)

The SMWW was used as wastewater model for a secondary effluent matrix. The composition of SMWW was prepared considering the work of Sánchez-Montes et al. [12], as well as receipts described in Zhang *et al.* [13] and in APHA Standard Methods [14] with modifications. The following chemicals were used:

i) inorganics salts: NaHCO₃ (96 mg L⁻¹), MgSO₄ (60 mg L⁻¹), NaCl (580 mg L⁻¹), and K₂HPO₄ (7.0 mg L⁻¹), CaSO₄·2H₂O (60 mg L⁻¹) and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (23.6 mg L⁻¹), KCl (4 mg L⁻¹).

ii) organic matter: beef extract (1.8 mg L⁻¹), peptone (2.7 mg L⁻¹), humic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹), sodium lignin sulfonate (2.4 mg L⁻¹), sodium lauryl sulphate (0.9 mg L⁻¹), tannic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹) and acacia gum powder (4.7 mg L⁻¹).

Some of the physicochemical parameters of the produced SMWW can be seen below:

Table S4 Physicochemical parameters of SMWW effluent

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	7.43 – 7.50 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	1,309 µS cm ⁻¹ (20.8 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)*	2.76 ±0.33

*Total organic carbon (TOC) measurement carried out as described in [1].

Text S2

UHPLC chromatographic conditions and Q-TOF/MS analyses for elucidation of IMD oxidation byproducts

Samples at varying treating times were analyzed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatograph (UHPLC – from Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic separation was performed using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA). The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). The chromatographic gradient used was as follows: 0-2 min, 20% B; 2.1-2.5 min, from 20 to 50% B; 2.5-7.0 min, from 50%-90% B. Column oven and autosampler temperatures were both set to 25 °C. The mobile phase flow and injection volume were 0.40 mL·min⁻¹ and 0.20 μL, respectively.

Mass spectra were obtained using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface and operated in the positive ion mode using a capillary voltage that varied from 2.0 to 3.0 kV. Table S3 shows the parameter values used during MS experiments that were optimized for the IMD standard.

Table S5 Q-ToF MS parameter values

Parameter	Value
Desolvation gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Gas temperature	250 °C
Nebulizer pressure	30 psi
Sheath gas temperature	275 °C
Sheath gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Nozzle voltage	115 V
Fragmentor voltage	60 V
Skimmer voltage	30 V
Octopole RF peak voltage	250 V
Collision energy	2 to 5 V

Molecular ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data were collected in a range of 50 to 600 Da, with a sweep rate of 3.0 spectrum s⁻¹ and processed by MassHunter Workstation Software, version B.08.00.

Text S3

UHPLC chromatographic conditions and Q-TOF/MS analyses for elucidation of DMPO oxidation byproducts

The presence of radical (mainly HO•) oxidizing species were confirmed by UHPLC-QTOF MS and ESR measurements and using DMPO as spin probe. All experiments were performed using 10 mL of deionized H₂O (pH 7). In a typical experiment, 1.25 mg of CoFe₂O₄ and 1.54 mg of PMS (corresponding to 0.125 g L⁻¹ of CoFe₂O₄ and 500 μmol L⁻¹ of PMS) were transferred to a 20 mL glass vial. Then, 10 mL of ultrapure H₂O (pH 7) was added to the flask to start the reaction under vigorous stirring. After 1 min reaction, 125 μL of a 4 mol L⁻¹ DMPO solution (final concentration of 100 mmol L⁻¹) were added to a 5 mL of the resultant solution and the mixture was left under stirring for an additional 1 min. After this time, 1 mL of sample was transferred to a plastic vial that was centrifuged for 15 s at 8000 rpm. For the homogeneous process, *i.e.*, when using Co(II) ions, 10 mL of a Co(NO₃)₂•6H₂O solution (replacing 10 mL of ultrapure H₂O) was used (corresponding to a final concentration of 200 μg L⁻¹ of Co(II) ions). Then, the same procedure (including PMS amount) was adopted, except the centrifugation step to remove the solid material. More experimental details can be seen in [15].

UHPLC analyses were carried out using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA) as stationary phase. The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). A gradient elution mode at 0.350 mL min⁻¹ was used to separate the main products according to the following sequence: 0-1 min, 5% B; 1-10 min, 95% B; 10-10.1 min, 95-5% B; and 10.5-13 min, 5% B. The injection volume, column, and autosampler temperatures were set to 1.0 μL and 35 °C, respectively. Qualitative analyses were performed using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface, operated in positive ion mode using a capillary voltage of 2.0 kV. The desolvation gas flow and gas flow in the cone were 11 and 10 L min⁻¹, respectively. For the mass confirmation of the detected byproducts, the collision energies ranged from 5 V to 16 V. Other variables such as source temperature, fragmentation voltage, skimmer voltage, and nozzle voltage were set to 300 °C, 40 V, 35 V and 225 V, respectively. Molecular and fragment ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode.

Data collected were analyzed ranging from 50 to 600 Da and processed by the MassHunter Workstation Software version B.08.00 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

ESR measurements were performed on a Varian E-109 X-band spectrometer, using a rectangular cavity at room temperature. A 200 μL flat quartz cell was used to analyze samples from the test experiments.

Text S4

Use of 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid to quench 1O_2

The adopted procedure was similar to the one described in Text S3. In a typical experiment, 1.25 mg of $CoFe_2O_4$ was transferred to a 20 mL glass vial. Then, 10 mL of ultrapure H_2O (pH ~ 8.3 spiked with 125 mmol L^{-1} NaOH solution) was added to the flask under vigorous stirring. After 1 min reaction, $40\ \mu\text{L}$ of a 100 mmol L^{-1} ABDA solution (final concentration of 0.4 mmol L^{-1}) were added and the mixture was left under stirring for an additional 1 min. The UV vis spectra corresponding to this point was set to “ $t = 0$ min”. Then, 1.54 mg of PMS (corresponding to $500\ \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS and to a final pH value close to 7) was added to start reaction. UV vis spectra were obtained every 5 min. For the homogeneous process, the same procedure was adopted except for the 10 mL of a $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ solution (replacing 10 mL of ultrapure H_2O) corresponding to a final concentration of $200\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Co(II) ions). No pH corrections were carried out during measurements, since it resulted in variations in the UV vis spectra of ABDA.

The reaction between ABDA and produced 1O_2 species, with gradual attenuation of the UV vis bands, is [16]:

Text S5

The short-chain carboxylic acids were determined by HPLC. For such, a Rezex™ ROA-H column (300 mm × 7.8 mm i.d., 8 μm particle size, from Phenomenex®) as the stationary phase and a 2.5 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ solution as the mobile phase were used at 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The carboxylic acids were identified by comparing their retention times with those of previously analyzed standards. The injection volume, detection wavelength, and the temperature of the column were 25 μL, 210 nm, and 23 °C, respectively.

Inorganic ions were also analyzed by HPLC with a conductivity detector (Shimadzu CDD-10A SP). For anion determination, a Shodex SI-52 4E column at 45 °C and 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂CO₃ solution at 0.8 mL min⁻¹ was used as the stationary and mobile phases, respectively. For this analysis, a chemically suppressor system (Thermo Scientific™ ACRS 500) pumping a regenerating solution of 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ at 0.8 mL min⁻¹ was used. Concerning cation determination, a Shodex YS-50 column at 40 °C and a mixture of 4.0 mmol L⁻¹ oxalic acid and 6.0 mmol L⁻¹ tartaric acid solution at 1.0 mL min⁻¹ were used, as the stationary and mobile phase, respectively, without the suppressor system.

Fig. S2 Histogram of the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (CMF) nanoparticles prepared by the Sol-gel (SG) and Co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C and 700 °C for 1 h (see inset).

Table S6 Mean particle size of the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (CMF) nanoparticles obtained from **Fig. S2**.

Material	Mean particle size / nm
SG 400 °C/1 h	9 ±3
SG 700 °C/1 h	86 ±7
Cpt 400 °C/1 h	10 ±1
Cpt 700 °C/1 h	23 ±9

a)

b)

Fig. S3 High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images of the as-prepared **a)** SG 400 °C/1 h, **b)** SG 700 °C/1 h, **c)** Cpt 400 °C/1 h, and **d)** Cpt 700 °C/1 h samples.

c)

d)

Fig. S3 (*continuation*) High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images of the as-prepared **a)** SG 400 °C/1 h, **b)** SG 700 °C/1 h, **c)** Cpt 400 °C/1 h, and **d)** Cpt 700 °C/1 h samples.

Fig. S4 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD card N° 98-010-9045 of CoFe_2O_4 .

Fig. S5 FTIR spectra the as-prepared CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S6 High-resolution spectra of O 1s for the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S7 High-resolution spectra of Co $2p_{3/2}$ for the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S8 High-resolution spectra of Fe 2p_{3/2} for the as-prepared CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S9 High-resolution spectra of C 1s for the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S10 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using distinct PMS concentration values (see inset) without CoFe_2O_4 . **Conditions:** 50 mg L^{-1} IMD, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 , 150 mL of treating solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption.

Fig. S11 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction), b) PMS consumption, and c) evolution of pH (for the condition with no pH control) as a function of treatment time (t) in the presence (w/ = with) or absence (w/o = without) of a phosphate buffer solution (see inset) using the CMF (cobalt magnetic ferrite) material prepared by the Sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h (SG 400 °C/1 h). **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 150 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig S11 (continuation) a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction), b) PMS consumption, and c) evolution of pH (for the condition with no pH control) as a function of treatment time (t) in the presence (w/ = with) or absence (w/o = without) of a phosphate buffer solution (see inset) using the CMF (cobalt magnetic ferrite) material prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h (SG 400 °C/1 h). **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 150 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark with manual pH corrections.

Table S7 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) for the experiments in **Fig. S11** and **Fig. S13** (see below).

Conditions	$k_{1st} / \text{min}^{-1}$	R^2
SG 400 °C/1 h: w/buffer – pH 7	0.53	0.99
SG 400 °C/1 h: w/o buffer – pH 7	0.14	0.99
SG 400 °C/1 h: w/o buffer – no pH control	0.020	0.97
[Co(II)] = 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$: w/ buffer – pH 7	0.26	0.99
[Co(II)] = 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$: w/o buffer – pH 7	0.11	0.97
[Co(II)] = 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$: w/o buffer – no pH control	0.039	0.97

Table S8 Concentration of Co and Fe ions determined by the ICP-OES technique in degradation experiments of Fig. 4 using the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (see manuscript).

Samples ID	[Co] / mg L^{-1}	[Fe] / mg L^{-1}
SG 400 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	0.097	0.043
SG 400 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total)	0.19	0.057
SG 700 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	0.05	0.032
SG 700 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total)	0.049	0.036
Cpt 400 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	0.098	0.281
Cpt 400 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total)	0.128	0.159
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	0.172	0.306
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total)	0.117	0.13

QL = Quantification limit for both metals: $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

DL = Detection limit for both metals: $4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

Fig. S12 Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) using distinct Co(II) ion concentration values (see inset – dilution factor of 2). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 µmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF when SG 400 °C/1 h compound was used. No repetitions were carried out. CMF = cobalt magnetic ferrite (CoFe₂O₄).

Fig. S13 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction), **b)** PMS consumption, and **c)** pH monitoring as a function of treatment time (t) in the presence (w/ = with) or absence (w/o = without) of a buffer solution using distinct Co(II) ion concentration values (see inset). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 7.0 (see inset), 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄ (see inset) and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark with manual pH corrections.

Text S6

Carbonization of CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite (CMF) nanoparticles using glucose and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)

CMF nanoparticles previously prepared by the Cpt method (thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h) were mixed and ground with glucose using two different proportions (CMF to glucose, in mass: 1:0.25 (Cpt: 700 °C/1 h: glucose (1:0.25)) and 1:1 (Cpt: 700 °C/1 h : glucose (1:1)) – see below). After grinding and homogenizing in an Agata mortar, the powder was transferred to a Al₂O₃ crucible that was placed inside a quartz tube. Then, the latter was connected to gas hoses and put inside a tube furnace. The treating temperature and time were adjusted to 600 °C during 30 min.

Concerning the samples that were previously prepared by the Sol-gel method and using PVA, the obtained powder from the Sol-gel synthesis were ground (not previously heat treated) in an Agata mortar and transferred to a Al₂O₃ crucible. Then, the latter was placed in a quartz tube that was connected to gas hoses and put inside a tube furnace. The treating time was set to 1 h and the target temperature was adjusted to 400 °C and 700 °C. Thus, two samples were prepared and labeled as SG400 °C/1 h@C and SG700 °C/1 h@C.

In all reported procedures and before the heating program, the system was left under a constant N₂ flow for 20 min (purging step). The same N₂ gas flow was set also during the heating and cooling steps. The heating rate was set to 15 °C min⁻¹.

Fig. S14 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using CMF nanoparticles previously obtained from the Cpt method (Cpt 700 °C/1 h) and carbonized in an anoxic atmosphere (N_2 gas). The carbon source was glucose at a mass ratio of 1:0.25 (Cpt: 700 °C/1 h : glucose (1:0.25)) and 1:1 (Cpt: 700 °C/1 h : glucose (1:1)). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μ mol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of CMF. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. The Cpt 700 °C/1 h data was included for comparison purposes.

CMF = cobalt magnetic ferrite (CoFe₂O₄).

Fig. S15 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using CMF nanoparticles previously obtained from the SG synthesis and carbonized in an anoxic atmosphere (N_2 gas). The carbon source was the resulting powder of the SG synthesis that was carbonized at 400 °C (SG 400 °C/1 h@C) and 700 °C (SG 700 °C/1 h@C) for 1 h. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the solid materials. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption.

CMF = cobalt magnetic ferrite (CoFe₂O₄).

Table S9 Concentration of Co and Fe ions determined by the ICP-OES technique for the degradation experiments of Fig. **Fig. S14** and **Fig. S15** (see manuscript for more details) using the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite.

Samples ID	[Co] / mg L^{-1}	[Fe] / mg L^{-1}
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption), without glucose	0.273	0.0669
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total), without glucose	0.313	0.0450
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption), 1:0.25 (glucose) <i>m/m</i>	1.19	0.704
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total), 1:0.25 (glucose) <i>m/m</i>	5.03	1.25
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption), 1:1 (glucose) <i>m/m</i>	0.769	0.141
Cpt 700 °C/1 h, $t = 2$ h (4 h in total), 1:1 (glucose) <i>m/m</i>	0.828	0.139
SG 400 °C/1 h@C (after 2 h adsorption)	0.103	0.0748
SG 400 °C/1 h@C (4 h in total)	0.175	0.0918
SG 700 °C/1 h@C (after 2 h adsorption)	0.0384	0.0635
SG 700 °C/1 h@C (4 h in total)	0.0559	0.0653

QL = Quantification limit for both metals: $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

DL = Detection limit for Co and Fe ions were 6 and $4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively.

Fig. S16 a) TEM images of the resulting powder of the SG synthesis that was carbonized at 700 °C for 1 h (SG 700 °C/1 h@C) and **b)** HRTEM image of a selected area showing a nanoparticle that is *i)* completely exposed and *ii)* possibly exhibiting a carbon layer (see details in the micrograph).

Fig. S17 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and b) PMS consumption in a simulated municipal wastewater model effluent matrix as a function of treatment time (t) using Co(II) ions and CMF nanoparticles previously obtained from the SG synthesis and carbonized at 700 °C for 1 h (SG 700 °C/1 h@C) in an anoxic atmosphere (N₂ gas). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 µmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C, and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 700 °C/1 h@C sample. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption.

Fig. S18 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption in tap water as a function of treatment time (t) using CMF nanoparticles previously obtained from the SG synthesis and carbonized at 700 °C for 1 h (SG 700 °C/1 h@C) in an anoxic atmosphere (N_2 gas). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH_2PO_4 , 25 °C, and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 700 °C/1 h@C sample. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption.

Fig. S19 Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) of the main detected byproducts (5 in total) resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CoFe_2O_4 (SG 400 °C/1 h sample). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH_2PO_4 , 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h sample. CMF = cobalt magnetic ferrite (CoFe_2O_4).

Fig. S20 MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts (5 in total) resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CoFe_2O_4 (SG 400 °C/1 h sample): **a)** IMD, **b)** P1, **c)** P2, **d)** P3, **e)** P4 and **f)** P5. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h sample.

Fig. S20 (*continuation*) MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts (5 in total) resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CoFe₂O₄ (SG 400 °C/1 h sample): **a)** IMD, **b)** P1, **c)** P2, **d)** P3, **e)** P4 and **f)** P5. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h sample.

Table S10 Retention time, main detected intermediates (m/z) and error of the main detected byproducts resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CoFe_2O_4 (SG 400 °C/1 h sample).

#	Compound	t_r (min)	ESI mode		
			m/z	Attribution (ESI+)	Error (ppm)
1	P5	1.841	143.0358	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	9.0885
			114.0092	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2]^+$	
			107.0603	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{Cl}]^+$	
			78.0334	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{Cl}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2]^+$	
2	P2	6.139	230.0416	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	9.9980
			186.0420	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{N}_2\text{O}]^+$	
			169.0154	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NHNO}_2]^+$	
			148.0728	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{Cl}]^+$	
			141.0198	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2\text{NO}_2]^+$	
			126.0093	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{CH}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_2]^+$	
			272.0512	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	
225.0514	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2]^+$				
228.0522	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{N}_2\text{O}]^+$				
210.0406	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{N}_2\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$				
191.0906	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{Cl}]^+$				
100.0500	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{Cl}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}]^+$				
288.0464	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	10.4148			
244.0459	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{N}_2\text{O}]^+$				
241.0468	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2]^+$				
226.0346	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{OH}]^+$				
207.0851	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{Cl}]^+$				
189.0743	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{Cl}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$				
169.0140	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{OH}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_2]^+$				
5	IMD	6.762	256.0572	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	9.3728
			210.0629	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{HNO}_2]^+$	
			209.0567	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2]^+$	
			175.0960	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{HNO}_2-\text{Cl}]^+$	
			128.0251	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{HNO}_2-\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_3]^+$	
			99.0545	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{NO}_2-\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{ClN}]^+$	
			84.0551	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{HNO}_2-\text{Cl}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{N}]^+$	
			56.0496	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{HNO}_2-\text{Cl}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{N}]^+$	
6	P1	7.130	157.9985	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	11.3923
			140.0713	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{OH}]^+$	
			122.0227	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{Cl}]^+$	
			111.9939	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{COOH}]^+$	
			78.0334	$[\text{M}+\text{H}-\text{Cl}-\text{COOH}]^+$	

Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h sample.

Fig. S21 Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in Table S3: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0572), **b)** P1 (m/z 157.9985), **c)** P2 (m/z 230.0416), **d)** P3 (m/z 272.0512), **e)** P4 (m/z 288.0464), and **f)** P5 (m/z 143.0358).

Fig. S21 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in Table S3: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0572), **b)** P1 (m/z 157.9985), **c)** P2 (m/z 230.0416), **d)** P3 (m/z 272.0512), **e)** P4 (m/z 288.0464), and **f)** P5 (m/z 143.0358).

Fig. S21 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in Table S3: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0572), **b)** P1 (m/z 157.9985), **c)** P2 (m/z 230.0416), **d)** P3 (m/z 272.0512), **e)** P4 (m/z 288.0464), and **f)** P5 (m/z 143.0358).

Fig. S22 Extracted ion chromatogram of the main detected intermediates showed in Table S3 and at distinct treatment time 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90, and 120 min (from top to bottom). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h samples.

Fig. S23 Time evolution of the main detected carboxylic acids resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CoFe₂O₄ (SG 400 °C/1 h sample). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 25 °C and 0.125 g L⁻¹ of the SG 400 °C/1 h sample.

Fig. S24 a) Total ion chromatogram (TIC) and **b)** Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) of the main detected byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and oxygen radical species (produced by the reaction between CoFe₂O₄/Co(II) ions with PMS oxidant – see Text S4).

Fig. S25 MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and oxygen radical species (produced by the reaction between $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Co}(\text{II})$ ions with PMS oxidant): **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO[•]/2OH, **c)** DMPO, **d)** DMPO[•]/O, **e)** DMPO/OH, **f)** 2DMPO/-OH, **g)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **h)** 2DMPO/-H, and **i)** DMPO/-3H.

Fig. S26 Proposed fragmentation route for the main detected DMPO byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and oxygen radical species (produced by the reaction between $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Co(II)}$ ions with PMS oxidant): **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO•/2OH, **c)** DMPO-, **d)** DMPO•/O, **e)** DMPO/OH, **f)** 2DMPO/-OH, **g)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **h)** 2DMPO/-3H, and **i)** 2DMPO/-H.

Fig. S26 (continuation) Proposed fragmentation route for the main detected DMPO byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and oxygen radical species (produced by the reaction between $CoFe_2O_4/Co(II)$ ions with PMS oxidant): **a**) DMPO/2OH, **b**) $DMPO^{\bullet}/2OH$, **c**) DMPO, **d**) $DMPO^{\bullet}/O$, **e**) DMPO/OH, **f**) 2DMPO/-OH, **g**) 2DMPO/O-3H, **h**) 2DMPO/-3H, and **i**) 2DMPO/-H.

Fig. S27 Intensity as a function of magnetic field for distinct experiments using CMF nanoparticles (0.125 g L^{-1}) and $200 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Co(II) in the presence of PMS ($500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and DMPO. See Text S3 for further details.

Fig. S28 Evolution of dissolved oxygen as a function of time (t) using CMF nanoparticles (0.125 g L^{-1} of the SG $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$ sample) and $200 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Co(II) in the presence of PMS ($500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$). **Conditions:** No IMD addition, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. S29 Evolution of the UV vis spectra for the 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid (ABDA) compound in the presence of PMS (500 μmol L⁻¹) and without CMF or Co(II) ions. **Conditions:** No IMD addition, pH ~7 and without buffer - see Text S4 for further details.

Fig. S30 Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) using CMF (cobalt magnetic ferrite) prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C during 1 h (SG 400 °C/1 h) for the recycling test. **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF, 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 150 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S31 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite synthesized by the sol-gel (SG) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, SG 400 °C/1 h and SG 700 °C/1 h (see inset), respectively. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD card N° 98-010-9045.

Fig. S32 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite synthesized by the co-precipitation (Cpt) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, Cpt 400 °C/1 h and Cpt 700 °C/1 h (see inset), respectively. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD card N° 98-010-9045.

a)

b)

Fig. S33 High-resolution spectra of C 1s for the as prepared (AsP) and used (Us) CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite samples obtained by the **a)** Sol-gel (SG) and **b)** Co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S34 High-resolution spectra of O 1s for the as prepared (AsP) and used (Us) CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite samples obtained by the **a)** Sol-gel (SG) and **b)** Co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S35 High-resolution spectra of Co 2p_{3/2} for the as prepared (AsP) and used (Us) CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite samples obtained by the **a)** Sol-gel (SG) and **b)** Co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S36 High-resolution spectra of Fe 2p_{3/2} for the as prepared (AsP) and used (Us) CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite samples obtained by the a) Sol-gel (SG) and b) Co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S37 Peak areas of the surface bonding states obtained from the O 1s spectra (see **Fig. S34**) using the **a)** Sol-gel (SG) and **b)** Co-precipitation (Cpt) samples that were thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S38 Peak areas of the surface bonding states obtained from the Co $2p_{3/2}$ spectra (see **Fig. S35**) using the **a)** Sol-gel (SG) and **b)** Co-precipitation (Cpt) samples that were thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S39 Peak areas of the surface bonding states obtained from the Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra (see **Fig. S36**) using the **a**) Sol-gel (SG) and **b**) Co-precipitation (Cpt) samples that were thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S40 Electrode potential (vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl 3 mol L⁻¹) as a function of time for distinctly prepared CMF nanoparticles (see inset for further details). A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (corrected to pH ~7) solution at ambient conditions was used. The arrows indicate the moment (after 1 h) when PMS and IMD were added into solution.

Fig. S41 a) Complex plane, **b)** Bode plots for the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite samples (in the as prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the Sol-gel (SG) method and heat treated at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h, and **c)** the equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance. A 0.5 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

Fig. S42 a) Complex plane, **b)** Bode plots for the CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite samples (in the as prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the Sol-gel (SG) method and heat treated at 700 °C for 1 h, and **c)** the equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance. A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

a)

b)

Fig. S43 a) Complex plane, **b)** Bode plots for the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite samples (in the as prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the Co-precipitation (Cpt) method and heat treated at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h, and **c)** the equivalent circuit (see above) used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance. A 0.5 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

Fig. S44 a) Complex plane, **b)** Bode plots for the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite samples (in the as prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the Co-precipitation (Cpt) method and heat treated at 700 °C for 1 h, and **c)** the equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance. A 0.5 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

Fig. S45 Oxide charge transfer resistance (R_{oxide}) for the as prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) samples of the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite. The exposed area was close to 1 cm^2 . Error bars refer to three repetitions.

The R_{oxide} values for the SG 700 °C/1 h, Cpt 400 °C/1 h, and Cpt 400 °C/1 h conditions after use (Us) were not determined due to lack of fit.

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